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Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens

Deliverable D6.3

Report on FRACTESUS scientific and technical contributions

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¹ **Nature:** **R** -Document, report; **DEM** -Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC** -Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**; **ETHICS** -Ethics requirement; **ORDP** -Open Research Data Pilot; **DATA** -data sets, microdata, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** **PU** -Public; **CO** -Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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1 Introduction

Regarding the dissemination activities, the project aims to share its findings and the main scientific/technical results achieved throughout its four years of activity. The dissemination strategy consisted in the following aspects:

1. **Participation in relevant international conferences:** the project and its achievements were presented every year at top international conferences, such as (for example) ASME PVP Conference, European Conference on Fracture, etc. Besides, conferences whose contributions were indexed in recognized scientific databases (e.g., Scopus) were preferred.
2. **Contributions to national conferences and events:** in addition to the international events, efforts were made to disseminate project outputs locally, thus reaching to a broader audience.
3. **Scientific papers in indexed (JCR, Journal Citation Report) international scientific journals:** the papers were published as open as possible, so that there is full access to the information and the knowledge generated by FRACTESUS.
4. Creation of **technical documents** that are complementary to academic publications.

It is noteworthy that the vast majority of these dissemination efforts have been linked to OpenAIRE (www.openaire.eu), the Open Access Infrastructure for research in Europe. For this task a proper Open Access plan was defined at the beginning of the project.

2 Participation in conferences/events

The project consortium has participated in **26** events, providing **38** presentations, covering international conferences and other types of events.

International conferences:

1. 1st Virtual European Conference on Fracture 2020. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Sergio Cicero (UC).
2. ASME Pressure Vessels & Piping Conference 2021. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Tomasz Brynk (SCK-CEN).
3. 20th International Conference on Fusion Reactor Materials 2021. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Sergio Cicero (UC).
4. 23rd European Conference on Fracture 2022. Contribution(s): **2**. Speaker(s): Marcos Sánchez (UC).

5. 5th Iberian Conference on Structural Integrity 2022. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Marcos Sánchez (UC).
6. Nuclear Material Conference 2022. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Timo Metzler (KIT).
7. 10th Euratom Conference on Reactor Safety & 10th Euratom Conference Radioactive Waste Management. **1**. Speaker(s): Tomasz Brynk (SCK-CEN).
8. ASME Pressure Vessels & Piping Conference 2022. **1**. Speaker(s): Tomasz Brynk (SCK-CEN).
9. 31st International Conference on Metallurgy and Materials 2022. **1**. Speaker(s): Gintautas Dundulis (KTU).
10. 27th International Conference on Fracture and Structural Integrity 2023. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Marcos Sánchez (UC).
11. ASME Pressure Vessels & Piping Conference 2023. Contribution(s): **7**. Speaker(s): Marcos Sánchez (UC), Sergio Cicero (UC), Aniruddh Das (HZDR), Frideriki Naziris (NRG), Timo Metzler (KIT).
12. 7th International Conference of Engineering Against Failure 2023. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Sergio Cicero (UC).
13. 21st International Conference on Fracture and Damage Mechanics 2023. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Ding Zhou (PSI).
14. 6th International Small Sample Test Techniques Conference 2023. Contribution(s): **2**. Speaker(s): Sergio Cicero (UC).
15. 21st International Conference on Fusion Reactor Materials 2023. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker: Timo Metzler (KIT).
16. 2nd International Symposium on Risk Analysis and Safety of Complex Structures and Components 2023. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Bernadett Spisák (BAY).
17. STRUMAT-LTO Summer School 2024. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Sergio Cicero (UC).
18. ASME Pressure Vessels & Piping Conference 2024. Contribution(s): **5**. Speaker(s): Sergio Cicero (UC), Florian Obermeier (Framatome), Susan Ortner (UKAEA), Audrey Somera (IRSN), Pentti Arffman (VTT).

Other events:

1. National Conference “Congreso del Grupo Español de Fractura” 2021. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Borja Arroyo (UC).
2. French colloquium MECAMAT 2023. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Audrey Somera (IRSN).
3. INCEFA-SCALE Training Seminar 2023. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Sergio Cicero (UC).
4. National Conference “Congreso del Grupo Español de Fractura” 2023. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Marcos Sánchez (UC).

5. Invited lecture at “Grupo de tecnología de Materiales del Instituto Nacional de Investigaciones Nucleares (México)” 2023. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Sergio Cicero (UC).
6. National Conference “Congreso del Grupo Español de Fractura” 2024. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Marcos Sánchez (UC).
7. Invited lecture at STRUMAT LTO Summer School “Testing and evaluation of LWR RPV embrittlement to support LTO” 2024. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Sergio Cicero (UC).
8. National Conference “16ème Colloque National en Calcul des Structures, CSMA2024”, 2024. Contribution(s): **1**. Speaker(s): Audrey Somera (IRSN).

3 Summary of publications

The project consortium has generated in **13** papers on scientific journals indexed in the Journal Citation Report (JCR), **22** papers included in conference proceedings indexed in Scopus, and **6** additional non-indexed publications. Details are as follows:

3.1 Papers in indexed (JCR and Scopus) scientific journals

1. E. Altstadt, F. Bergner, M. Houska, Use of the small punch test for the estimation of ductile-to-brittle transition temperature shift of irradiated steels, Nuclear Materials and Energy 26 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nme.2021.100918>.
2. M. Li, I. Uytendhouwen, T. Pardoën, R. Chaouadi, M. Lambrecht, Effect of the pre-crack non-uniformity on the initiation of brittle fracture in mini-CT specimen, Engineering Fracture Mechanics 290 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2023.109457>.
3. M. Li, R. Chaouadi, L. Noels, I. Uytendhouwen, M. Lambrecht, T. Pardoën, Effect of pre-crack non-uniformity for mini-CT geometry in ductile tearing regime, Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics 126 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tafmec.2023.103946>.
4. A. Das, P. Chekhonin, M. Houska, F. Obermeier, E. Altstadt, Master curve testing of RPV steels using mini-C(T) specimens – Irradiation effects and censoring statistics, Nuclear Materials and Energy 34 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nme.2023.101395>.
5. M. Li, R. Chaouadi, I. Uytendhouwen, T. Pardoën, Size correction scheme to determine fracture toughness with mini-CT geometry in the transition regime, Engineering Fracture Mechanics 290 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2023.109486>.
6. T. Brynk, I. Uytendhouwen, R. Chaouadi, Simple inverse FEM based procedure of flow curve extraction applied to unirradiated and irradiated 73 W weld material, Engineering Fracture Mechanics 289 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2023.109400>.
7. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, M. Kirk, E. Altstadt, W. Server, M. Yamamoto, Using Mini-CT Specimens for the Fracture Characterization of Ferritic Steels within the Ductile to Brittle Transition Range: A Review, Metals (Basel) 13 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/met13010176>.

8. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, A. Cimentada, On the use of mini-CT specimens to define the Master Curve of unirradiated reactor pressure vessel steels with relatively high reference temperatures, *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics* 124 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tafmec.2022.103736>.
9. E. Altstadt, An Improved Correlation for the Estimation of the Yield Strength from Small Punch Testing, *Metals* 13 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/met13101716>.
10. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, Mini-C(T) specimens for Master Curve analysis of structural steels operating within their ductile-to-brittle transition region, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 298 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2024.109917>.
11. R. Chaouadi, J. Schuurmans, Critical analysis of the mini-CT geometry for fracture toughness characterization of the 73W high-copper submerged-arc weld in the unirradiated and irradiated condition, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 298 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2024.109929>.
12. S. Ortner, M. Sánchez, J. Echols, S. Cicero, P. Checkhonin, Validity of Toughness Measurements From Miniature Specimens Failing in Different Fracture Modes, *Journal of Pressure Vessel Technology, Transactions of the ASME*, 146(5), 051501 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4065854>.
13. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, F. Obermeier, M. Serrano, Y.L. Chiu, E. Altstadt, On the possibility of extending the crack length criterion in the master curve methodology, *Journal of Pressure Vessel Technology* (2024), Under review.

3.2 Papers in indexed (Scopus) conference proceedings

1. S. Cicero, M. Lambrecht, H. Swan, P. Arffman, E. Altstadt, T. Petit, F. Obermeier, B. Arroyo, J.A. Álvarez, R. Lacalle. Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens: FRACTESUS project, *Procedia Structural Integrity*, Elsevier B.V. (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2020.10.008>.
2. T. Brynk, M. Lambrecht, I. Uytendhouwen, P. Arffman, E. Altstadt, T. Petit, FRACTESUS Project: General Framework of Materials Selection and Testing Processes, Volume 4: Materials and Fabrication, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2021-61906>.
3. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, S. Arrieta, Master curve evaluation of ANP-5 steel using mini-CT specimens, *Procedia Structural Integrity*, Elsevier B.V. (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2022.12.027>.
4. T. Brynk, I. Uytendhouwen, P. Arffman, E. Altstadt, R. Kopriva, F. Obermeier, M. Serrano, FRACTESUS Project: Final Selection of RPV Materials for Unirradiated and Irradiated Round Robins, Volume 1: Codes and Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2022-83871>.
5. G. Dundulis, E. Narvydas, V. Leišis, T. Petit, Estimation of the loading conditions to fracture behaviour, 31st International Conference on Metallurgy and Materials, METAL (2022). <https://doi.org/10.37904/metal.2022.4409>.

6. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, S. Arrieta, FRACture mechanics TESting of irradiated RPV steels by means of SUB-sized Specimens: FRACTESUS PROJECT, *Procedia Structural Integrity*, Elsevier B.V. (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2022.12.003>.
7. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, G. Bonny, H. Swan, P. Lappalainen, E. Altstadt, T. Petit, F. Obermeier, FRACTESUS Project overview: objectives, organisation and initial findings, *Procedia Structural Integrity*, Elsevier B.V. (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2023.06.034>.
8. B. Spisák, Z. Bézi, R. Erdei, S. Szávai, Modification of VCCT method with implementation of GTN model for the determination of J-integral, *Procedia Structural Integrity*, Elsevier B.V. (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2023.07.125>.
9. G. Bonny, E. Altstadt, P. Arffman, S. Cicero, F. Obermeier, T. Petit, H. Swan, R. Chaouadi, E. Gaganidze, B. Hargitai, M. Kolluri, R. Kopriva, P. Rozsahegyi, M. Serrano, P. Spätig, I. Uytendhouwen, H. Wilcox, M. Yamamoto, Present Status of the Fractesus Project: Round Robin on Unirradiated Materials, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-105449>.
10. Metzler, E. Gaganidze, J. Aktaa, Numerical Prediction of Fracture Toughness of a Reactor Pressure Vessel Steel Based on Experiments Using Small Specimens, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-105918>.
11. F. Naziris, R. Hernandez Pascual, T. Metzler, E. Gaganidze, I. Uytendhouwen, M. Kolluri, Master Curve Evaluation Using Miniature C(T) Specimens as Part of a Round Robin Program Within the FRACTESUS Project, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-107254>.
12. M. Li, R. Chaouadi, I. Uytendhouwen, T. Pardoen, G. Bonny, The Effect of Loss of Constraint on the Initiation of Ductile Fracture in a Mini-CT, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-106216>.
13. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, Fracture Characterization of Structural Steel S275JR Using Conventional CT Specimens, Mini-CT Specimens and Small Punch Specimens: A Comparison, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-105437>.
14. A. Das, P. Chekhonin, M. Houska, F. Obermeier, E. Altstadt, Fractography of Neutron Irradiated RPV Steels – A Comparison of Shift in Reference Temperature and Net Hardening, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-103648>.
15. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, S. Arrieta, Literature Review on Testing of Mini-CT Specimen to Characterize the Ductile-to-Brittle Transition Range and the Upper Shelf Regime, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-105596>.

16. D. Zhou, D. Jiang, P. Spätig, H.-P. Siefert, On the determination of the reference temperature T₀ of the Master-Curve method using sub-sized compact tension specimens, *Procedia Structural Integrity*, Elsevier B.V., (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2023.12.044>.
17. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, Fracture characterization of structural steel S690Q by using mini-CT specimens, *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2692/1/012003>.
18. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, F. Obermaier, M. Serrano, Y-L. Chiu, E. Altstadt, On the possibility of extending the crack length criterion in the master curve methodology, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2024).
19. G. Bonny, I. Uytendhouwen, E. Altstadt, P. Arffman, S. Cicero, F. Obermeier, T. Petit, P. François, B. Tanguy, H. Swan, H. Wilcox, Present status of the Fractesus Project: Numerical and Experimental Round Robins on Irradiated and Unirradiated Materials. Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2024).
20. A. Somera, F. Péralès, P-G. Vincent, Simulation of crack growth in mini-C(T) fracture tests in the ductile-to-brittle transition using a cohesive zone model: application to reactor pressure vessel steels, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2024).
21. F. Obermeier, I. Uytendhouwen, G. Bonny, E. Altstadt, S. Cicero, M. Sánchez, J. Echols, Fractesus Project: Fracture Toughness Round Robin on a High Copper Weld Using Miniature C(T) Specimens – Results and Discussion, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2024).
22. S. Ortner, M. Sánchez, J. Echols, S. Cicero, P. Checkhonin, Validity of Toughness Measurements From Miniature Specimens Failing in Different Fracture Modes, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2024).

3.3 Other (non-indexed) publications

1. E. Réka, B. Zoltán, FRACTESUS projekt: Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens, *Anyagvizsgálók Lapja* (2022). <https://www.anyagvizsgaloklapja.hu>
2. B. Arroyo, S. Cicero, M. Lambrecht, H. Swan, P. Arffman, E. Altstadt, T. Petit, F. Obermeier, Caracterización en fractura de aceros de vasija mediante probetas mini-CT y small punch. Primeros pasos del proyecto europeo FRACTESUS, *Revista Española de Mecánica de la Fractura*. Volumen 2, pp. 49-54 (2021). ISSN: 2792-4246.
3. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, FRACTESUS: fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens, *Revista Española de Mecánica de la Fractura*, Volumen 3, pp. 65-70 (2022). ISSN: 2792-4246.

4. T. Brynk, F.J.P. Lopez, A. McLennan, Increase of nuclear installations safety by better understanding of materials performance and new testing techniques development (MEACTOS, INCEFA-SCALE, and FRACTESUS H2020 projects), EPJ Nuclear Sciences and Technologies 8 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjn/2022033>
5. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, Caracterización a fractura de los aceros estructurales S355J2 y S460M mediante el uso de probetas mini-C(T). Revista Española de Mecánica de la Fractura. In press. (2023).
6. A. Somera, F. Perales, P-G. Vincent, Simulation de la propagation de fissure lors d'essais de rupture de type mini-C(T) dans le domaine de transition ductile-fragile à partir d'une approche cohésive : application aux aciers de cuves de réacteurs, CSMA 2024 - 16ème Colloque National en Calcul des Structures, CNRS, CSMA, ENS Paris-Saclay, CentraleSupélec, Giens, France (2024).

4 Data management

The last dissemination activity carried out in the project was the publication of testing results in Zenodo – Open Aire (open access platforms). This makes possible to the scientific community to take advantage of the large dataset generated in FRACTESUS for further analysis and research. To achieve this goal several deliverables and reports were prepared thought the project:

- S. Cicero, B. Arroyo. Data Management Plan (DMP) – 1st version. FRACTESUS Consortium (grant number 900014), Deliverable D6.8, WP6, UC/PR N°15 (2021).
- S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, M. Sánchez, G. Díaz. Testing protocols and reporting formats. FRACTESUS Consortium (grant number 900014), Deliverable D6.9, WP6, UC/PR N°15 (2021).
- S. Cicero, B. Arroyo. How to publish in FRACTESUS project – Open Access Procedure, WP6, UC/PR N°15 (2021).

With all this, more than 600 datasets were uploaded to these platforms, each one with its corresponding DOI. The general links are shown below:

<https://explore.openaire.eu/search/find/projects?fv0=FRACTESUS&f0=q>
<https://zenodo.org/search?q=fractesus&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=bestmatch>

5 Conclusions

FRACTESUS dissemination activities have been intense and diverse. It is noticeable the high effort made for the whole consortium for sharing the results of the project, with a total of 41 scientific contributions to journals and conferences, together with hundreds of available data for the research community. More scientific contributions are expected in the upcoming months.